

PORTFOLIO OF SERVICES

ENACT

Partners:

The project “ENACT - Enhancing the capacity of civil society organizations to support victims of anti-LGBTQI hate crimes” (reference code 101141894) is co-funded by the European Commission under the call CERV-2023-CHAR-LITI of the Citizens program, Equality, Rights and Values Program.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Introduction

Hate crimes against LGBTIQ+ individuals profoundly affect not only survivors but also their communities and society at large. The ENACT project—Enhancing the Capacity of Civil Society Organisations to Support Victims of Anti-LGBTQI Hate Crimes—seeks to address these impacts by equipping civil society organisations (CSOs) with tools to collaborate effectively with public authorities. This partnership aims to enhance support mechanisms for survivors, combat revictimisation, and address the overlapping factors of discrimination through an intersectional approach.

The ENACT research underlined the growing recognition across the European Union of the urgent need to address the rising incidence of hate crimes and discrimination targeting LGBTQI individuals. Despite legal frameworks that safeguard fundamental human rights, many victims of anti-LGBTQI+ violence and bias-motivated incidents still face significant barriers when seeking justice, protection, and support. These barriers include underreporting, limited institutional response, insufficient specialised services, societal stigma, and lack of knowledge of procedures and available services.

In response, the present document introduces a Portfolio of Services aimed at ensuring that all Member States deliver, either directly or through partnerships with civil society organisations, a minimum standard of support to victims of anti-LGBTQI+ hate crimes and discrimination, in alignment with the Victims' Rights Directive (Directive 2012/29/EU).

The Portfolio of Services provides essential and practical information on the core areas of support available to victims of anti-LGBTQI+ hate crimes and discrimination. It outlines a comprehensive range of services, including psychosocial assistance, legal aid, and advocacy—all of which are vital for addressing the immediate and long-term needs of victims. Designed with accessibility and usability in mind, the Portfolio allows users to easily navigate the different types of services offered, organised by area of focus—such as mental health, legal rights, and social reintegration. Each service entry includes clear descriptions, eligibility criteria (where applicable), and contact details, enabling individuals to promptly connect with the respective providers. Whether victims are seeking emotional support, legal representation, or simply guidance on available options, the Portfolio serves as a practical, user-centred tool that empowers them to take the first steps toward safety, justice, and recovery.

GREECE

Psychological Helpline "11528-By Your Side"

Contact details:

Tel: 11528, Email: diplasou@11528.gr

Address: 4, Agiou Isidorou, Str., 114 71 Athens

Opening Hours: Monday - Friday, 10:00-19:00

Services: Telephone Psychological Support 2.Online & Face-to-Face Counselling Sessions

Link: <http://11528.gr/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Mental health support for LGBTQI+ individuals

Positive voice - Empowerment Group

Contact details: Tel: 210 32 34 492, Email: empowerment@positivevoice.gr

Address: 4, Pittaki Str., Athens, 105 54

Opening Hours: Monday - Friday, 10:00-14:00

Services: Peer support from others living with HIV for shared understanding and empowerment: 1. Information on HIV medication, hospitals and doctors specialized in HIV care, health insurance coverage, pension-related procedures, navigating Disability Certification Centers (KE.P.A.) and related processes, welfare benefits and allowances e.g., public transport cards, university access 2. Updates on laws and policy changes affecting HIV-positive individuals 3. Documentation of discrimination cases for rights advocacy 4. Referrals to other services and organizations when needed

Link: <https://positivevoice.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: HIV/AIDS awareness, prevention, and support

Rainbow School

Contact details:

Email: info@rainbowschool.gr

Address: 15, Viktoros Ougko Str., Athens, 104 37

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Manage issues that arise on the school site regarding LGBTQ+ identity of children, teachers, and/or parents/guardians. Our help is about the steps that can be taken to address such incidents in the school setting. Training schools/caregivers on issues related to LGBTQ+ inclusion.

Link: <http://rainbowschool.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Inclusive education & safe spaces for LGBTQI+ youth

Positive voice

Contact details:

Tel: 210 86 27 572 Email: info@positivevoice.gr

Address: 13, Ag. Anargiron str., Athens, 105 54

Opening Hours: Monday - Friday, 09:00-17:00

Services: 1. Psychosocial support for people Living with HIV: 16–20 free psychological support sessions in-person & online access 2. Referral to external services 3. ChemSex Support: Risk reduction & safer drug use practices - Peer counseling & harm reduction kits (syringes, gloves, condoms, lube) - Info on drugs, overdose response, sexual consent - Support managing or reducing drug use - Free testing for HIV & hepatitis

Link: <https://positivevoice.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Empowerment and advocacy for people living with HIV

Rainbow Families

Contact details:

ouraniotoksofamilies@gmail.com,

rainbowfamnorth@gmail.com (North Greece),

rainbowfamilies.crete@gmail.com (Crete)

Tel: 6977185161

Address: 58, Konstantinoupoleos Ave., Athens, 11854

Opening Hours: Under appointment

Services: 1. Support for (prospective) LGBTQI+ parents, single and separated 2. Provision of information and resources 3. Community for adult children of LGBTQI+ parents 4. Support for parents of LGBTQI+ children 5.

Advocacy & Awareness raising

Link: <http://www.rainbowfamiliesgreece.com/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Support for LGBTQI+ families and same-sex parenting

HIV Support Group

Contact details:

Email: gpapadopetrakis@positivevoice.gr, Tel: 2108627572

Address: 4, Pittaki Str., Athens, 105 54

Opening Hours: Under Appointment (210 32 34 492)

Services: 1. Self-help/peer-support groups for people living with HIV - Identification and advocacy of participants' needs. -Bi-monthly group meetings to discuss everyday life concerns and challenges.

Link: <https://positivevoice.gr/positive-point>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Peer support and care for individuals living with HIV

HIV Support Group

Contact details:

Email: amanolopoulou@positivevoice.gr, Tel: 2315525020
Address: 112, Egnatia Ave., 546 22, Thessaloniki, (3rd floor)
Opening Hours: Under Appointment
Services: 1. Self-help/peer-support groups for people living with HIV - Identification and advocacy of participants' needs. -Bi-monthly group meetings to discuss everyday life concerns and challenges.
Link: <https://positivevoice.gr/positive-point>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: Peer support and care for individuals living with HIV

Thess Checkpoint

Contact details:

Tel: 2310 282 284
Address: 112, Egnatia Ave., 546 22, Thessaloniki
Opening Hours: Tuesday-Friday, 12:00-19:30, Saturday 12:00-16:00
Services: 1. Free of charge HIV and Hepatitis B and C testing 2. Counselling 3. Awareness raising activities
Link: <https://mycheckpoint.gr/?lang=en>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: HIV & STI testing and sexual health services (Thessaloniki)

Ref Checkpoint

Contact details:

Email: Tel: 210 3243133 Email: info@refcheckpoint.gr
Address: 200, Michail Voda str., Athens, 10446
Opening Hours: Tuesday, Wednesday & Friday, 16:00 - 20:00
Services: Medical examination for HIV, Hepatitis B and C for refugees and migrants. All information is available in Arabic, Urdu, Farsi, Dari, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Russian and English.
Link: <https://refcheckpoint.gr/>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: HIV & STI testing and sexual health services for refugees/migrants

Positive voice

Contact details:

Tel: 2315 525 020 Email: info@positivevoice.gr
Address: 112, Egnatia Ave., 546 22, Thessaloniki
Opening Hours: Monday - Friday, 09:00-17:00
Services: 1. Psychosocial support for people Living with HIV: 16–20 free online psychological support sessions
 2. Referral to external services
 3. ChemSex Support: Risk reduction & safer drug use practices - Peer counseling & harm reduction kits (syringes, gloves, condoms, lube) - Info on drugs, overdose response, sexual consent - Support managing or reducing drug use - Free testing for HIV & hepatitis
Link: <https://positivevoice.gr/positive-point>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: Psychosocial support

Ath Checkpoint

Contact details:

Tel: 210 33 10 400
Address: 4, Pittaki Str., Athens, 105 54
Opening Hours: Tuesday - Saturday, 12:00 - 20:00
Services: 1. HIV and Hepatitis B and C testing 2. Counselling
Link: <https://mycheckpoint.gr/ath-checkpoint/>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: HIV & STI testing and sexual health services (Athens)

Red Umbrella Thessaloniki

Contact details:

Tel: +302310282284 redumbrellathens@gmail.com
Address: 112, Egnatia Ave., 546 22, Thessaloniki
Opening Hours: Every Monday, 16.00-18.00
Services: Testing for HIV, hepatitis B & C and syphilis
 Sexual health counseling
 Provision of free condoms and pregnancy tests
 Direct link to health & welfare services
 Psychological support
 Social support
 Legal support
 Counseling on addiction and harm reduction issues
 Provision of safer drug use materials
 Provision of free clothing and other basic necessities
 Artistic & recreational activities
 Beauty services (make-up, hairdressing, manicure, etc.)
Link: <https://redumbrella.org.gr/>
Helpline: NO
Area of Focus: Rights and support for sex workers

Red Umbrella Athens

Contact details:

Tel: +306971977971 redumbrellathens@gmail.com

Address: 200, Michail Voda Str., Athens, 104 46

Opening Hours: Every Wednesday, 14:00–20:00

Services: Psychological support

Social support

Legal support

Counseling on addiction and harm reduction issues

Provision of safer drug use materials

Provision of free clothing and other basic necessities

Artistic & recreational activities

Beauty services (make-up, hairdressing, manicure, etc.)

Link: <https://redumbrella.org.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Rights and support for sex workers

Greek National Commission for Human Rights

Contact details:

Email: info@nchr.gr , Tel: 21 0723 3221

Address: 6, Neofitou Vamva Str., Athens, 106 74

Opening Hours: Contact via telephone

Services: 1. Monitoring human rights developments, 2.

Advisory role to the Greek State, 3. Public awareness and education, 4. Support in international reporting, 5.

Promotion of legal and political reform

Link: <https://www.nchr.gr/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: National human rights institution

Intersex Greece

Contact details:

E-mails: info@intersexgreece.org.gr

(not really often) , intersexgreece@gmail.com

Tel: +30 697 7660860

Address: 1) 57, Andritsenis str.,11146, Athens

(Administration offices) 2) 12, Vasileos Konstantinou Sq., 17121, Athens, (Members' space of support)

Opening Hours: Upon Appointment

Services: 1. Education & Training: In collaboration with the

Colourful School or independently, Intersex Greece provides tailored educational programs for: organizations,

school communities, educators, policymakers, and spiritual

leaders, 2. Peer Support: A private Facebook group for

intersex people, families, and allies - Smaller closed

support circles, especially for new parents - Opportunities

for peer connection via forums and social media. 3.

Advocacy, Human Rights & Legal Reform

Link: <https://intersexgreece.org.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Gender equality and LGBTQI+ advocacy

G-All (Gender Alliance Initiative)

Contact details:

Tel: 6977 092546, 211 111 5107, Email: info@g-all.gr

Address: 18-22, Pithodorou str., Athens 104 41

(Administration offices)

Opening Hours: Upon Appointment

Services: 1. Educational and training programs on gender

diversity and LGBTQAI+ rights, 2. Counseling sessions

(including LGBTQAI+-focused support), 3. Activist initiatives

and campaigns for LGBTQAI+ equality and visibility, 4.

Networking and interconnection with LGBTQAI+

communities and allies, 5. Consulting sessions on LGBTQAI+

inclusion and gender diversity

Link: <https://g-all.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Gender equality and LGBTQI+ advocacy

Racist Violence Recording Network

Contact details:

Tel: 2107233216, Email: racistviolence@nchr.gr

Address: 6, Neofitou Vamva Str., Athens, 106 74

Opening Hours: Contact via telephone

Services: 1. Systematic recording of racist violence, 2.

Monitoring hate crimes against human rights defenders, 3.

Legal, medical, and social support via member

organizations 4. Trainings & Seminars

Link: <https://rvrn.org/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Monitoring and combating racist and hate violence

Police Action for Human Rights-LGBTQI+

Contact details:

Through the form in the website

Address: 45, Mezonos Str., Athens, 10438

Services: 1. Defense of Human Rights and abolition of

discrimination based on sexual orientation, gender identity,

and gender characteristics

2. Publications (printed or digital) supporting LGBTQAI+

rights and awareness

3. Online presence (website) for LGBTQAI+ advocacy and

information

4. Public events and discussions promoting LGBTQAI+

inclusion and anti-discrimination

Link: <https://policeaction.gr/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: LGBTQI+ rights and police accountability

Rainbow Seniors

Contact details:

Email: info@rainbowseniors.eu Tel: 694 8540931

Address: 45, Charilaou Trikoupi str., 106 81, Athens

Opening Hours: From September on Info Desk with opening hours

Services: 3. Physical examination, 4. Social Pharmacy, 5. Solidarity group

Link: <https://rainbowseniors.eu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Support and advocacy for elderly LGBTQI+ individuals

HUNGARY

Háttér Society Legal aid service

Contact details: jogsegely@hatter.hu

voicemail: +36 1 6333 454

Address: 1136 Budapest, Balzac u. 8-10.

Opening Hours: Continuous monitoring of voicemail and emails

Services: Free legal assistance and information for victims of discrimination, harassment or abuse based on sexual orientation or gender identity, and in all cases where the sexual orientation or gender identity of the person seeking assistance may be relevant.

Link: <https://hatter.hu/jogsegely>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: LGBTIQ-specific legal assistance

Háttér Society Social support service

Contact details: via contact form [in Hungarian](#) / [in English](#) or szocialissegites@hatter.hu

voicemail: + 36 1 6333 414

Address: 1061 Budapest, Székely Mihály u. 11.

Opening Hours: Upon appointment or walk-in opportunity on Tuesdays between 9:00-11:00

Services: The service provides assistance to LGBTIQ people using individual social work methods to solve practical problems arising in the areas of employment, healthcare, housing and administrative matters.

Link: <https://hatter.hu/tevekenysegunk/szocialis-segito-szolgalat>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Social work (healthcare, administration, housing, employment)

Háttér Society Information and counselling hotline

Contact details: lelkisegely@hatter.hu

137-37, +36 1 329 33 80

Address: 1136 Budapest, Balzac u. 8-10.

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day between 18:00-23:00

Services: Help with self-acceptance, coming out, family, relationship, school or work conflicts.

Link: <https://hatter.hu/lelkisegely>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Mental health

Transvanilla Transgender Association

Contact details: szervezet@transvanilla.hu

Address: no public address

Opening Hours: n.a.

Services: An organisation representing the interests of transgender, gender non-conforming and intersex people. Provides legal assistance and information.

Link: <https://transvanilla.hu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Legal assistance, psychosocial assistance, counselling, events

Háttér Society Personal counselling

Contact details: [via contact form](#)

Address: 1136 Budapest, Balzac u. 8-10.

Opening Hours: Upon appointment

Services: Mental health support through individual in-person counselling sessions for a maximum period of 10-12 weeks.

Link: <https://hatter.hu/szemelyes>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Mental health

White Ring Public Benefit Association

Contact details: fehergyuru@t-online.hu

Address: 1055 Budapest, Szt. István krt. 1.

Opening Hours: Monday - Thursday 9:00-16:00, Friday 09:00-12:30

Services: Legal, psychological and financial assistance for victims in need.

Link: <https://fehergyuru.eu/en/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Legal, psychological and financial assistance

Prizma Transgender Association

Contact details: kapcsolat@prizma.lgbt

Address: no public address

Opening Hours: n.a.

Services: Online peer-support meetings and in-person community events for trans and non-binary people.

Link: <https://prizma.lgbt/kapcsolat/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Community support

Trauma Centre

Contact details: info@traumakozpont.hu

Address: 1126 Budapest, Derkovits u. 10.5, Viktoros Ougko Str., Athens, 104 37

Opening Hours: n.a.

Services: An organisation providing psychiatric, psychotherapeutic, psychological treatment and psychosocial counselling to traumatised Hungarian citizens and their family members. It offers favourable prices to disadvantaged clients.

Link: <https://traumakozpont.hu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Mental health

Partiscum Association for the LGBT Community in Szeged

Contact details: info@szegedilmbt.hu

+36 30 797 8019

Address: Szeged, no public address

Opening Hours: Phone service: Monday - Friday 10:00-16:00

Services: Association providing information and legal assistance to LGBTIQ people in Szeged.

Link: <https://szegedilmbt.hu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Legal assistance and orientation

Diverse Youth Network

Contact details: info@diverseyouthnetwork.eu

+ 36 30 914 5007

Address: 7626 Pécs, Béni Balogh Ádám út 3/10.

Opening Hours: Phone service: Monday - Friday 11:00-17:00

Services: Organisation offering basic counselling and support to LGBTIQ people in Pécs.

Link: <https://diverseyouthnetwork.eu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Orientation and community support

Cifra-LGBTQ Community Kecskemét

Contact details: info@cifralmbtg.hu

Address: Kecskemét, no public address

Opening Hours: n.a.

Services: Organisation offering basic counselling and support to LGBTIQ people in Kecskemét.

Link: <http://cifralmbtg.hu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Orientation and community support

Cívicolors

Contact details: civiscolors@gmail.com

Address: 4029 Debrecen, Baross Gábor u. 17.

Opening Hours: n.a.

Services: Organisation offering basic counselling and support to LGBTIQ people in Debrecen.

Link: <https://www.civiscolors.hu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Orientation and community support

Hungarian Helsinki Committee

Contact details: helsinki@helsinki.hu

+36 1 321 4323, +36 1 321 4327, or +36 1 321 4141

Address: 1074 Budapest, Dohány u. 20.

Opening Hours: Phone service: Monday - Friday

In-person assistance upon appointment

Services: Legal assistance for foreign nationals, asylum seekers, refugees, detainees, or in relation to police interventions or abuse.

Link: <https://helsinki.hu/segitseg-kerese/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Legal assistance

Hungarian Civil Liberties Union

Contact details: jogsegely@tasz.hu

+36 1 279 2235

Address: 1136 Budapest, Tatra u. 15/b.

Opening Hours: Phone service: Tuesday 13:00-15:00 and Thursday 10:00-12:00

In-person assistance upon appointment

Services: Legal assistance in cases of discrimination by a public agent; related to healthcare, education, disability, Roma origin, social status, or poverty.

Link: <https://tasz.hu/ingyenes-jogsegelyszolgalat/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Legal assistance

Victim Support Services

Contact details: email addresses available at:

[https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059)

[?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059) (after clicking on the name)

+36 80 225 225

Address: Addresses available at:

[https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059)

[ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059)

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day 00:00-24:00

In-person opening hours available at:

[https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059)

[illetekesege=&ugykor=5059](https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/ugyfelszolgalatok?illetekesege=&ugykor=5059)

Services: Victim Support Services in Hungary operate at the capital and county levels as part of government offices.

They provide: information about victims' rights, obligations, and options; emotional support; interpretation and translation assistance; legal advice and practical assistance; guidance to access legal representation; certification of victim status; and potential immediate financial assistance in crisis situations.

Link: <https://kormanyhivatalok.hu/aldozatsegitoszolgalatok>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Orientation, mental health, interpretation and translation, legal advice, facilitation of legal representation, official certification, financial assistance

Victim Support Centres

Contact details: email addresses available at:
<https://vansegitsegitseg.im.gov.hu/elerhetosegek/>
 +36 80 225 225

Address: Addresses available at:
<https://vansegitsegitseg.im.gov.hu/elerhetosegek/>

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day 00:00-24:00
 In-person opening hours available at:

<https://vansegitsegitseg.im.gov.hu/elerhetosegek/>

Services: Victim Support Centres provide personalised information about the public victim support system and services, as well as emotional support, with the involvement of a psychologist if necessary. They are currently available in 23 Hungarian municipalities.

Link: <https://vansegitsegitseg.im.gov.hu/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Orientation, mental health

National Crisis Management and Information Telephone Service

Contact details: okit@segelyszervezet.hu
 +36 80 20 55 20

Address: 1221 Budapest, Kossuth Lajos u. 64.

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day 00:00-24:00

Services: Helpline for the victims of domestic violence or human trafficking.

Link: <https://okit.hu/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Immediate assistance, shelter

Péterfy Sándor Utcai Hospital-Outpatient Clinic, Crisis Intervention and Psychiatric Department

Contact details: +36 70 934 1051

Address: 1074 Budapest, Alsó erdősor u. 7.

Opening Hours: Appointments can be made by phone, Monday - Friday 09:00-15:00

Services: Outpatient crisis therapy, regardless of place of residence, for people in a state of psychological crisis who are currently facing challenging life situations or losses that they are unable to resolve on their own, and who may even be suffering from suicidal thoughts.

Link: <https://peterfykh.hu/osztaly/krizisintervencios-es-pszichiatrai-osztaly-43>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Mental health

The Office of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights

Contact details: panasz@ajbh.hu
 +36 1 475 7100, +36 80 215 000 (Toll free number)

Address: 1055 Budapest, Falk Miksa u. 9-11.

Opening Hours: Monday - Thursday 08:00-16:00, Friday 08:00-12:00

Services: A body investigating activities and omissions by state bodies and public service providers that violate fundamental rights.

Link: <https://ajbh.hu>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Legal and practical assistance, orientation, potential remedies

Kék Vonal (Blue Line) Child Crisis Foundation

Contact details: info@kek-vonal.hu

116 111 (for youth - under 24 years old), 116 000 (for adults - above 24 years old)

Address: 1054 Budapest, Szemere u. 21.

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day 00:00-24:00

Services: Mental health support and practical counselling to children and youth, parents, and related professionals. Thematic areas include but are not limited to crisis, abuse, family relationships, anxiety, sexual and reproductive health, sexual orientation, or gender identity.

Link: <https://kek-vonal.hu/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Mental health, orientation, counselling

Office of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights, Directorate-General for Equal Treatment

Contact details: egyenlobanasmod@ajbh.hu

+36 1 475 7100 or +36 1 475 7129, +36 80 215 000 (Toll free number)

Address: 1055 Budapest, Falk Miksa u. 9-11.

Opening Hours: Monday - Thursday 08:00-16:00, Friday 08:00-12:00

Services: The Directorate-General responsible for investigating conduct that violates the requirement of equal treatment and constitutes discrimination or harassment.

Link: <https://www.ajbh.hu/en/ebff>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Official report, investigation, potential remedies

Office of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights, Directorate-General for Police Complaints

Contact details: panasz@ajbh.hu

+36 1 475 7100, +36 80 215 000 (Toll free number)

Address: 1055 Budapest, Falk Miksa u. 9-11.

Opening Hours: Monday - Thursday 08:00-16:00, Friday 08:00-12:00

Services: Directorate-General investigating complaints concerning police measures violating fundamental rights, failure to take such measures, and the use of coercive measures.

Link: <https://www.ajbh.hu/en/rendeszeti-foigazgatosag>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Official report, investigation, potential remedies

Budapest Housing Office

Contact details: lakhatasi.iroda@budapest.hu

+36 1 999 8428

Address: 1052 Budapest, Bárczy István u. 1-3.

Opening Hours: Monday 12:00-18:00, Tuesday 08:00-16:30, Wednesday 08:00-18:00, Thursday 08:00-16:30, Friday 08:00-14:00

Services: Housing advice, orientation, and social work for tenants of municipal properties, refugees, and citizens of the capital city whose housing is at risk.

Link: <https://budapest.hu/eselyteremto-budapest/elerheto-lakhatas/fovarosi-lakhatasi-iroda>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Social work, housing advice

Dózsa Temporary Accommodation

Contact details: +36 1 238 9500

Address: 1134 Budapest, Dózsa György út 152.

Opening Hours: Social support assistance: every day 00:00-24:00

Services: Individual social work and mental health support. Social support services available 24 hours a day. Day center, night shelter, temporary accommodation.

Link: <https://www.bmszki.hu/hu/dozsa-atmeneti-szallas>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Social work, mental health, temporary accommodation

Menhely (Shelter) Foundation

Contact details: +36 1 338 4186

Address: 1082 Budapest, Vajdahunyad utca 3.
(central address - services at different locations)

Opening Hours: Phone service: every day 00:00-24:00

Services: Helpline for temporary accommodation, food and hygiene facilities, health services, official paperwork.

Link: <https://menhely.hu/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Social work, temporary accommodation

ITALY

Rete Lenford – Avvocatura per i Diritti LGBTI+

Contact details: info@retelenford.it

Address: Via Paleocapa 11, Bergamo

Opening Hours: sos@retelenford.it

Services: Legal support, strategic litigation, advocacy, training for professionals

Link: <https://www.retelenford.it/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Legal and Rights Assistance for LGBTI+ victims

Casa dei Diritti

Contact details:

rainbow.desk@cooplotto.org

Address: Via De Amicis n. 10 – 20123 Milano

Opening Hours: Monday from 10:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m.; Thursday from 2:30 p.m. to 5:30 p.m.

Services: Support to LGBTQIA+ individuals aged 18–35 who have been estranged from their families of origin due to their sexual orientation and/or gender identity.

Link: <https://www.comune.milano.it/aree-tematiche/servizi-sociali/casa-dei-diritti>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: LGBTI youths

Centro Anti Discriminazioni Mo.N.Di

Contact details:

info@cadmondi.com phone 320 112 5749

Address: via Abbrescia 13, Bari, Italy

Opening Hours: Contact via email or via phone

Services: Support to LGBTI persons, victim of discrimination

Link: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100087333798234>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Anti-discrimination, Social & Legal Support

Refuge LGBT – Roma Capitale & Croce Rossa

Contact details: info@gaycenter.it

Address: Via San Giovanni in Laterano, Rome

Opening Hours: 24/7 (on-call housing emergency access)

Services: Temporary shelter, legal/psychosocial support, job orientation, support for youth expelled from families

Link: <https://gaycenter.it/servizi/refuge/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Emergency housing for LGBTI persons at risk

MIT - Movimento Identità Trans

Contact details:

info@mit-italia.it, Tel: 051 649 3880

Address: Via Polese 22, 40122 Bologna

Opening Hours: Mon–Thu, 14:30–18:30

Services: Trans support services, legal and health orientation, anti-violence support

Link: <https://www.mit-italia.it/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Trans Health, Anti-violence, Legal Support

Circolo Maurice – Sportello Migranti LGBT+

Contact details: segreteria.maurice@gmail.com

Address: Via Stampatori 10, 10122 Torino

Opening Hours: Tues–Thurs 15:00–19:00

Services: Support for LGBTQI+ asylum seekers and refugees: housing, legal, trauma, social inclusion, anti-racism

Link: <https://www.mauricegbtq.org/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Asylum, migration, racialized LGBTQI+ persons

Fondazione LILA Milano

Contact details: sportelloiris@lilamilano.it

Address: Via Carlo Maderno 4, Milan

Opening Hours: Monday to Wednesday 9-13,
Thursday 14-18, Friday 9-13329 5870862

Services: Support to LGBTIQ+ persons. Harm reduction, legal aid, health referrals

Link: <https://www.lilamilano.it>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: LGBTI health

iKEN Onlus

Contact details: segreteria@i-ken.it

Address: Via Antonio Genovesi 36 - Napoli

Opening Hours: online 24h

Services: Project "QUESTA CASA NON E' UN ALBERGO"
(Property confiscated from the mafia "in memory of Silvia Ruotolo and all the innocent victims of the mafia")

Shelter for LGBTI people victims of persecution, abuse or violence due to their sexual orientation or gender identity

Link: <https://www.i-ken.org/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Shelter home for LGBTI people

Anemone Centro Antiviolenza

LGBTQIA+

Contact details: info@associazioneanemone.it

Address: Ex-Fila Conessioni Metropolitane
Via Leto Casini 11, Firenze

Opening Hours: Online

Services: Support to people of the LGBTQIA+ community who are facing discrimination or relational violence.

Link: <https://associazioneanemone.it/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Discrimination and relational violence

ALTRE SPONDE CENTRO DI ASCOLTO

Contact details: info@altresponde.it

Address: c/o circolo Arci di Porta al Prato, Via delle PortenNuove 33, Firenze

Opening Hours: online 24h

Services: Support for LGBTQIA+ persons in Florence

Link: <https://www.altresponde.it/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Support and helpline

LITHUANIA

National LGBTI Rights

Organization LGL

Contact details: info@gay.lt

Address: Odminių g. 11-4, LT-01122, Vilnius

Opening Hours: I-VI 9.00-17.00

Services: LGBTIQ rights Advocacy, trainings, legal consulting, strategic litigation

Link: <https://lgl.lt/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Consultations for LGBTIQ persons

Trans Autonomija

Contact details:

transautonomija@gmail.com

Address: Online

Opening Hours: Online

Services: General transgender community support

Link: <https://transautonomija.lt/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: General transgender community support

Lithuanian Red Cross

Contact details: info@redcross.lt

Address: Konstitucijos pr. 7A, PC Europa, III a. Vilnius, LT-09307

Opening Hours: I-VI 8.30-17.30

Services: Legal support for non-Lithuanian victims of hate crime

Link: <https://redcross.lt/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Asylum, migration, racialized LGBTQI+ persons

List of State-accredited support services in Lithuania

Contact details: N/A

Address: N/A

Opening Hours: N/A

Services: General support to victims of crime, needs assessment, emotional support, emergency housing.

Link: <https://vrm.lrv.lt/lt/pagalba-nukentejusiems-nuusikalstamu-veiku/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: General support services for victims of crime

SLOVENIA

LEGEBITRA | LGBTIQ+ advocacy

Contact details: Tel: +386 30 361 281 and +386 40 494 858 (legal counseling); Email: svetovalnica@legebitra.si and pravna.svetovalnica@legebitra.si (legal counseling)

Address: Trubarjeva 76a, Ljubljana

Opening Hours: **Youth center:** Monday–Wednesday: 13:00–18:00; Thursday: 13:00–21:00; Friday: 13:00–22:00; psychosocial and legal counseling: Monday – Friday: 10:00–16:00;

Services: Psychosocial support and counseling, legal counseling for LGBT individuals, HIV and other STI testing, and education on LGBT-related topics.

Link: <https://legebitra.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Legebitra is a civil society LGBTIQ+ organization working in the fields of human rights, education, mental, physical, and sexual health. It advocates for social and systemic change based on respect for sexual orientation, gender identity, and/or gender expression. In its work, it takes into account the intersectionality of other personal circumstances such as health status, nationality, race or ethnic origin, language, religion or belief, disability, age, social status, financial situation, education, or any other personal circumstance.

My Rainbow Institute

Contact details: Email: info@mojamavrica.si

Address: Jarška cesta 14, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Program for Psychosocial Support, Co-Creating Solutions and Empowerment

Link: <https://mojamavrica.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: LBTQ+ women-founded and LBTQ+ women-led transfeminist organization that values inclusivity and celebrate diversity. Focuses on supporting individuals with fewer opportunities, particularly within the LGBTIQ+ community. They offer a range of services including psychosocial support, counseling, and community-building activities, all grounded in transfeminist principles.

Transfeminist Initiative TransAkcija

Contact details: Email: info@transakcija.si

Address: Trg prekomorskih brigad 1, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Support services for trans individuals and educational programs for professionals.

Link: <https://transakcija.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: TransAkcija provides information about transgender identities, advocates for trans persons' rights in Slovenia, offers services for gender-diverse individuals, equips allies with tools, and promotes trans activism.

Institute for Culture of Diversity Open

Contact details: Email: zavod.open@gmail.com

Address: Maistrova 8, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Research and advocacy

Link: <https://www.open.si/ozavodu/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Research, advocacy and campaigning related to human rights, culture, social security and the economic system.

Association DIH – Equal Under the Rainbow

Contact details: Tel: +386 41 562 375; Email: info@dih.si

Address: Slomškova ulica 25, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday: Closed; Tuesday–Friday: 11:00–16:00

Services: Support groups, counseling, information sharing.

Link: <https://www.dih.si/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: DIH's activities include communication, publishing, political activities, socializing, sports, recreation, cultural activities, arts, entertainment, and creativity in areas related to LGBTIQ+ individuals. They offer integration, inclusion, and socialization of diverse sexual orientations, gender identities, and gender expressions, as well as the promotion and protection of human rights, equality, and activism.

Fršlus Association

Contact details: Email: drustvofrslus@gmail.com

Address: Vanča vas 76, 9251 Tišina

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Providing safe spaces where LGBTIQ+ individuals can meet and share experience, organizing workshops, educational programs, cultural events, and spaces for open dialogue aimed at overcoming prejudice, fostering understanding of diversity, and empowering all individuals—especially young LGBTIQ+ people and those who are part of both the LGBTIQ+ and Roma communities.

Link: <https://frslus.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The Fršlus Association was established with the aim of connecting and empowering LGBTIQ+ individuals in the Pomurje region, as well as raising awareness and providing information about LGBTIQ+ topics within the community and among the broader public.

Out in Slovenia – Sports, recreation and socializing for LGBTIQ+

Contact details: Email: info@outinslovenija.com

Address: Slomškova 25, Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: The sports association Out in Slovenia engages in sports, recreation, health, culture, and human rights, with a focus on activities for the LGBTIQ+ community.

Link: <https://www.outinslovenija.com/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Out in Slovenia offers various activities focused on sports, recreation, and socializing, primarily for the LGBTIQ+ community and its allies, as well as advocacy and participation in projects.

Ljubljana Pride Association

Contact details: Tel: +386 40 773 586; Email: info@ljubljana-pride.org; pr@ljubljana-pride.org; sqvot@ljubljana-pride.org

Address: Dunajska cesta 10, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday–Friday; 9:00 –17:00

Services: Advocacy, education, organizing annual Pride Parade in Ljubljana, support groups, counseling, legal and administrative help.

Link: <https://ljubljana-pride.org/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Ljubljana Pride advocates for the human rights and interests of LGBTIQ+ individuals and operates as an independent, youth-led, volunteer-based, non-profit civil society organization. As the organizer of the annual Pride Parade, it is also responsible for coordinating safety measures and collecting reports of incidents during the Parade.

Association ŠKUC and clubs Tiffany and Monokel

Contact details: Email: kulturnicenterq@gmail.com

Address: Masarykova cesta 24, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Provides a safe space for the socialization of LGBTIQ+ community. The club offers its premises for regular meetings, parties, discussions, lectures, workshops, performances, exhibitions, debate and film evenings, festival events, literary readings, round tables, and various social and community-building activities.

Link: <https://www.kulturnicenterq.org/o-nas/tiffany/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: ŠKUC – Cultural Center Q is a project of Club Tiffany, run by the Student Cultural Association (ŠKUC). Cultural Center Q aims to promote creativity, artistic expression, and cultural engagement among Slovenian LGBTIQ+ individuals; to present and document Slovenian LGBTIQ+ art and culture; to place Slovenian LGBTIQ+ art and culture on the global map; to connect with LGBTIQ+ artists and cultural centers abroad; and to explore and support subcultures and alternatives within the LGBTIQ+ community.

Koroška Pride (Center for Equality Development)

Contact details: Email: koroska.paradaponosa@gmail.com

Address: Gozdarska cesta 99, 2382 Mislinja

Opening Hours: Contact via email/facebook

Services: Koroška Pride, Center for Equality Development, is the first and only LGBTIQ+ organization in the Koroška region and the only non-governmental organization primarily focused on the needs of the LGBTIQ+ community in rural Slovenia.

Link: <https://www.facebook.com/koroskapride>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Koroška Pride is committed to upholding the principles of equality and representation of (sexual) minorities, promoting diversity in the social and cultural landscape of Koroška region, improving the quality of life for LGBTIQ+ individuals, decentralizing LGBTIQ+ activism in Slovenia, and participating in more inclusive policies and democratic governance of society.

Maribor Through Pink Glasses

Contact details: Email: info@mkc.si; Tel: +386 2 300 29 93; social media: <https://www.facebook.com/mariborskoziroznataocala/>; https://www.instagram.com/maribor_pride/

Address: Ob železnici 16, 2000 Maribor

Opening Hours: Contact via email or social media

Services: Maribor Through Pink Glasses is a regular program of MKC Maribor that addresses the needs of LGBTIQ+ youth in the region. Through information, literature, socializing, advice, and various activities, the program supports young people who are exploring and coming to terms with their sexual orientation or gender identity. It is open to anyone willing to participate and contribute in any way to the planning, preparation, and implementation of activities. Most activities take place at the following locations:

MKC Maribor (Ob železnici 16, 2000 Maribor)

Cultural Incubator (Koroška cesta 18, 2000 Maribor)

Link: <https://mkc.si/mb-skozi-roznata-ocala>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Organizing the Pride Parade in Maribor every two years, addressing the needs of LGBTIQ+ youth, and organizing social events and advice sessions for young people who are exploring and coming to terms with their gender identity and sexual orientation.

VigeVageKnjige (independent Slovenian publishing house)

Contact details: Tel: +386 70 61 05 39; Email:

mariborka@vigevageknjige.org;

Address: Mariborka: Koroška 6, 2000 Maribor; Šišklja: Runkova 2, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email/phone

Services: The publishing house VigeVageKnjige organizes workshops, performances, music events, and concerts in the spaces of Mariborka and Šišklja that are welcoming to LGBTIQ+ individuals.

Link: <https://vigevageknjige.org/en/about>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: VigeVageKnjige Publishing is one of the independent Slovenian publishers, specializing in comics and novels and catering to both children and adult audiences. Through its translations and original works, VigeVageKnjige highlights and challenges prejudices. They have established two physical bookstores: the first, named Mariborka, opened in Maribor in March 2023; the second, named Šišklja, opened in Ljubljana in November 2024.

Peace Institute

Contact details: Tel: +386 1 234 77 20; Email: info@mirovni-institut.si

Address: Metelkova 6, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email/phone

Services: Research, awareness-raising and advocacy for human rights, anti-discrimination and equality for all. Providing information on anti-LGBTIQ+ hate crime.

Link: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The Peace Institute – Institute for Contemporary Social and Political Studies – is an independent and non-profit research organization. It was founded in 1991 by a group of individuals who believed in the peaceful resolution of conflicts, equality, and respect for human rights. Through scientific research and public actions, the Institute strives to foster an open society capable of critical thinking and grounded in the principles of equality, responsibility, solidarity, human rights, and the rule of law.

Amnesty International Slovenia

Contact details: Tel: +386 1 426 93 77 Email: amnesty@amnesty.si

Address: Dunajska cesta 5, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email/phone

Services: Amnesty International Slovenia is part of a global movement that exposes and investigates human rights violations, educates and raises awareness, conducts campaigns, and mobilizes people for action.

Link: <https://www.amnesty.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Through powerful campaigns, it seeks justice for victims of abuse, holds perpetrators accountable, challenges repressive laws, and works to free those unjustly imprisoned. Amnesty stands as a voice for the silenced and oppressed, striving for a just world for all – including LGBTIQ+ community.

PIC – Legal Center for the Protection of Human Rights and the Environment

Contact details: Tel: +386 15211888 and +386 51681181; Email: pic@pic.si

Address: Metelkova 6, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday – Friday: 9:00 – 14:00

Services: PIC provides legal support to individuals and vulnerable groups in protecting their fundamental rights and strengthens the impact of NGOs in the fields of environmental protection and spatial planning, protection of vulnerable groups (including persons with disabilities, elderly, victims of domestic and gender-based violence, children, asylum seekers and refugees, etc.). PIC offers legal counselling and representation, as well as legal expertise in the area of asylum and migration.

Link: <https://pic.si/en/domov-english/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: PIC's main areas of focus are protection of vulnerable groups, asylum and migration, and environmental and climate protection.

Association for Non-violent Communication

Contact details: Tel: +386 1 4344 822 (Ljubljana); +386 5 6393 170 (Koper); Email: info@drustvo-dnk.si; dnk.koper@drustvo-dnk.si (Koper)

Address: Vojkova cesta 1, 1000 Ljubljana; Vojkovo nabrežje 10, 6104 Koper

Opening Hours: Available via phone every day 8:00 and 16:00.

Services: Providing information and counselling in the field of violence to victims, the general public, individuals unsure how to respond to violence, students, school staff, and other professionals, and with its helpline serves as a vital contact point for those unable to visit the office but in need of guidance or information.

Link: <https://shorturl.at/LAL23>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Association for Nonviolent Communication provides programs for people experiencing violence (including LGBTIQ+): expert consultations and discussions, lectures and seminars, intervention workshops, preventive workshops in schools, workshops for victims of violence, educational activities, activism and awareness raising.

Pandora's path Institute

Contact details: Tel: +386 41 625 446; Email: zavod@pandorinapot.si

Address: Cesta v Šmartno 6, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email/phone

Services: Pandora's path Institute is a non-governmental, non-profit organization dedicated to offering psychosocial support to individuals and groups (including LGBTIQ+) while fostering knowledge and skills that contribute to personal growth and development.

Link: <https://pandorinapot.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The work of the Pandora's path Institute is intended for everyone in need of support, with special attention given to women and migrant women, who often face additional barriers in the areas of equality, access to education, employment, and a safe environment. By promoting gender equality, advocating for women's rights, and creating a safe space for expression and connection, we aim to ensure equal opportunities for all.

Association SOS Helpline for Women and Children – Victims of Violence

Contact details: Tel: 080 11 55 | 24/7; Email: sostelefon@drustvo-sos.si

Address: Zaloška cesta 57, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Available 24 hours a day via phone (helpline).

Services: They offer direct victim support, counseling, safe housing and also a SOS Helpline which is a 24-hour confidential phone line primarily for women and children – victims of domestic and intimate partner violence – where people can seek help, support, and information about any form of violence, available support services, their rights, and the responsibilities of institutions.

Link: <https://drustvo-sos.si/>

Helpline: YES, 24 h/day

Area of Focus: Association SOS offers free individual psychosocial counseling, support from a psychotherapist, social advocacy, accompaniment to institutions, and the possibility of joining a support group. Women and children who are experiencing or have experienced domestic violence and/or sexual abuse in the past can participate.

Institute Emma – Help center for victims of violence

Contact details: Tel: 080 21-33 | 8:00-15:00 and 18:00-21:00; +386 1 425-47-32 (Ljubljana); +386 7 490-65-10 (Krško); Email: zavod.emma@siol.net; zavodemma.krsko@gmail.com (Krško)

Address: Krakovski nasip 26, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday-Friday: 8:00-15:00; Helpline 8:00-15:00 and 18:00-21:00

Services: Institute Emma offers psychosocial support via phone, as well as individual and group forms of assistance to victims of violence (including LGBTIQ+).

Link: <https://zavod-emma.si/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: In addition to providing professional psychosocial support to victims of violence, Institute Emma is also active in the field of prevention, believing that only a comprehensive approach can lead to the desired outcome – a society with zero tolerance for violence.

Slovene Philanthropy, Association for Promotion of Volunteering

Contact details: Tel: +386 1 430 12 88, +386 1 433 51 06; Email: info@filantropija.org

Address: Cesta Dolomitskega odreda 11, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday – Friday: 8:00 - 18:00

Services: Psychosocial support to vulnerable groups, advocacy, awareness raising, humanitarian aid, support with integration of migrants, education, counseling, information provision, healthcare services for the uninsured, etc.

Link: <https://www.filantropija.org/en/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Slovene Philanthropy runs programs in the fields of volunteering, migration (including integration support and advocacy), intergenerational cooperation, international cooperation, and operates a Pro Bono Clinic for people without health insurance (or without status).

Slovenian Red Cross

Contact details: Tel: +386 1 24 14 300 Email: rdeci.kriz@rks.si

Address: Mirje 19, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday-Friday: 8:00-15:30

Services: Psychosocial support and counseling in cases of sexual and gender-based violence, support for vulnerable individuals, assistance in the context of migration, provision of psychological first aid in the field of mental health for people from Ukraine, and organization of blood donation campaigns.

Link: <https://www.rks.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The mission of the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, including the Slovenian Red Cross, is to improve the lives of vulnerable people through the power of humanity. Guided by seven fundamental principles—humanity, impartiality, neutrality, independence, voluntary service, unity, and universality—the Slovenian Red Cross responds to distress in local communities, especially among vulnerable groups such as children and the elderly. It promotes respect for human dignity, encourages solidarity, supports healthy living, and provides education and training on its mission, the Red Cross movement, and international humanitarian law.

Ambasada ROG, a grassroots initiative in Ljubljana made up of local activists and migrants.

Contact details: Email: ambasada.rog@gmail.com

Address: Cigaletova 1, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Ambasada ROG offers free meals, assistance to foreigners with paperwork, language courses, and social support. They organize cultural events, concerts, dances, lectures, provide legal aid to asylum seekers, and run creative and sports workshops.

Link: <https://ambasada-rog.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Ambasada Rog is a non-institutional community and space in Ljubljana, established in 2016 as part of the broader Autonomous Factory Rog. It is a space of solidarity, led and co-created by migrants, refugees, activists, artists, volunteers, and supporters. It provides a LGBTIQ+ friendly space.

Society KLJUČ

Contact details: Tel: 080 17 22 | 9:00-13:00; Email:

info@drustvo-kljuc.si

Address: Povšetova ulica 37, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Monday-Friday: 9:00-13:00

Services: Society KLJUČ provides emergency assistance and care for victims of human trafficking, helps organize their return to their place of residence, offers free counseling to potential and actual victims, promotes health, encourages cooperation with law enforcement, supports witness protection, and assists with social and work (re)integration.

Link: <https://drustvo-kljuc.si/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Since 2001, Society KLJUČ has developed numerous preventive and support programs aimed at raising awareness among the general and professional public, as well as among potential and actual victims of human trafficking. They contribute to shaping policies and programs centered on the needs of victims of trafficking, forced marriage, labor exploitation, and individuals with experiences in prostitution.

8th of March Institute

Contact details: Email: institut8.marec@gmail.com

Address: Glinškova ploščad 9, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Contact via email

Services: Research, advocacy and awareness raising. The 8th of March Institute is known for its protest actions and petition campaigns addressing gender inequality and socio-economic disparities in society, as well as for training and involving volunteers in its initiatives.

Link: <https://www.8marec.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The 8th of March Institute is a nonprofit organization dedicated to exposing injustices, addressing social and gender inequalities, and advocating for human rights. Founded in 2016, the Institute initially aimed to raise awareness about the importance of equality. Over time, its mission evolved to include a broader focus on various issues related to gender, social justice, and systemic inequality, paired with concrete actions and demands for change.

TOM phone for children and adolescents

Contact details: Tel: 116 111; Email: tom@zpms.si

Address: Dimičeva ulica 9, 1000 Ljubljana (This is the address of the Association of Friends of Youth of Slovenia – Zveza prijateljev mladine Slovenije.)

Opening Hours: TOM phone operates every day, including Sundays and public holidays, from 12:00 to 20:00 at the toll-free number 116 111. TOM online chat is available Monday to Friday, according to the schedule published on the TOM website (<https://www.e-tom.si/stopi-v-stik#klepetalnica>). Children and adolescents can send an email to TOM at any time.

Services: TOM offers free, anonymous, and confidential counselling through three channels: phone, online chat, and email. Children and adolescents (including LGBTIQ+) can contact TOM with any distress, dilemma, or question they may have.

Link: <https://www.e-tom.si/>

Helpline: YES. Helpline operates every day from 12:00 to 21:00; Chat - Monday to Friday according to the schedule available here: <https://www.e-tom.si/stopi-v-stik#klepetalnica>.

Area of Focus: TOM provides emotional support to children and adolescents who face various questions, dilemmas, or challenges while growing up. Counsellors listen, offer guidance, work together with young people to find solutions, and when necessary, refer them to appropriate professional services.

Association for Psychological Counselling Kameleon

Contact details: Email: pogovor@svetovalnicakameleon.si

Address: Ulica škofa Maksimilijana Držečnika 6, 2000 Maribor

Opening Hours: Upon appointment

Services: The main activity of the association is psychological counselling, provided through an (anonymous) synchronous online counselling platform or via email. Counselling sessions are available five times a week and are publicly listed on the association's website.

Link: <https://svetovalnicakameleon.si/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: The Association for Psychological Counselling Kameleon is a voluntary, non-profit, and humanitarian organization that works for the benefit of children, adolescents, adults, and the elderly. The counsellors are volunteers—at minimum, graduates in psychology—who are properly trained to provide psychological counselling and information. Kameleon also produces psychological content in an engaging, popular science format, sharing it through articles on their website and social media platforms. They also offer online workshops, lectures, and roundtable discussions.

Samarijan Confidential Telephone Association

Contact details: Tel: 116 123; Email: samarijan@gmail.com

Address: Zaloška cesta 69, 1000 Ljubljana

Opening Hours: Available 24 hours a day via phone (helpline).

Services: The Samarijan Confidential Telephone Association offers support to individuals in distress, providing a confidential phone line available 24/7—including weekends and public holidays—through two dedicated lines. The association also engages in activities aimed at reducing the stigma around mental health in Slovenia.

Link: <http://www.telefon-samarijan.si/>

Helpline: YES, 24 h/day

Area of Focus: Samarijan Confidential Telephone Association offers a confidential phone call service for adults experiencing mental distress, along with various activities aimed at raising awareness and promoting understanding of mental health issues in Slovenia. It is a non-governmental, non-profit, humanitarian, and volunteer-based organization recognized as serving the public interest in social welfare.

SPAIN

Servicio 028 Arcoiris

Contact details: Phone number: 028

Address: No address

Opening Hours: 24 hours

Services: The 028 Arcoiris Service is a free, confidential, and fully accessible public helpline offering psychological, legal, and general support for victims of LGBTIphobic hate crimes and discrimination in Spain. Available 24/7 by phone, email, and online chat, it operates in multiple languages and is staffed by professionals with specialized training. The service aims to ensure that no one in Spain is left without support regarding issues related to sexual orientation, gender identity, or sex characteristics.

Link: <https://www.igualdad.gob.es/comunicacion/sala-de-prensa/igualdad-en-marcha-servicio-028-arcoiris-igtvi/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Basic, psychological and legal assistance.

Observatorio Madrileño contra la LGBTIfobia

Contact details: Phone number: 618 54 71 66

Address: C. de la Batalla del Salado, 37, 1º D, Arganzuela, 28045 Madrid

Opening Hours: Monday through Friday 9:00 to 17:00h.

Services: Observatorio Madrileño contra la LGBTIfobia offers support before, during, and after an LGBTIphobic attack. In the moment, they can provide emotional support, advice, and even accompany you to the police or hospital. After the incident, they offer legal guidance, counselling, and assistance in filing a complaint. Long-term support includes follow-up on legal proceedings, access to a specialized hate crime lawyer, and help managing media exposure if you wish to make a public report.

Link: <https://contraelodio.org/wp/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Psychological and legal assistance

Línea Arcoiris

Contact details: Phone number: 913 604 605

WhatsApp: 676 78 58 30

Address: Calle Chinchilla, 4, 1º Ext Izq, Madrid.

Opening Hours: Monday through Friday 8:00 to 15:00h.

Services: The Línea Arcoiris is a national support and information service run by FELGTB, a federation of LGBTI organizations in Spain. It focuses on assisting families, youth, and addressing LGBTIphobic hate crimes through three main programs: school-based violence prevention (Red Educa), support and research on family diversity, and the national SEIIS service for hate crime prevention. It also responds to inquiries related to sexual health, asylum requests, and documentation needs for LGBTI students and researchers.

Link: <https://felgtbi.org/que-hacemos/consulta/linea-arcoiris/>

Helpline: YES

Area of Focus: Information, assistance and sensitisation

Observatori contra l'LGtBI-fòbia

Contact details: Phone number: +34 932 172 669

Email: coordinacio@observatori.cat

Address: C/Comte Borrell 22, Barcelona

Opening Hours: Monday through Friday 10:00 to 14h and 16:00h to 20:00h.

Services: The Observatori Contra l'Homofòbia designs and implements a permanent monitoring system to combat discrimination, homophobia, biphobia, and transphobia in all areas where they may occur. They offer three main services: Victim Support, Complaints Office, and Training & Research.

Link: <https://observatori.cat/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Psychological and legal assistance

SAI Network

Contact details: To call your local SAI, look up the local contact information in the SAI Network webpage:

<https://igualtat.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/lgbti/xarxa-sai/>

Address: To turn to your local SAI, look up the local contact information in the SAI Network webpage:

<https://igualtat.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/lgbti/xarxa-sai/>

Opening Hours: It depends on each local SAI. To find out the opening hours of your local SAI, look up the local contact information in the SAI Network webpage:

<https://igualtat.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/lgbti/xarxa-sai/>

Services: The Xarxa de Serveis d'Atenció Integral LGBTI+ (SAI) of Catalonia is a comprehensive, high-quality, and community-based support network for individuals who experience, have experienced, or are at risk of discrimination or violence based on their sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression.

Link: <https://igualtat.gencat.cat/ca/ambits-dactuacio/lgbti/xarxa-sai/>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Psychological and socioeducational services.

Oficina Nacional de Lucha contra los Delitos de Odio

Contact details: -

Address: -

Opening Hours: Website information

Services: The National Office Against Hate Crimes provides a list of resources for victim support. In this website you can see the available services where you can turn to report a hate crime in each Spanish region.

Link: <https://oficinacional-delitosdeodio.ses.mir.es/publico/ONDOD/es/mapaRecursos.html>

Helpline: NO

Area of Focus: Resource map

For any support, please contact:

Spain - cisarecerca@udg.edu

Italy - info@retelenford.it

Slovenia - info@mirovni-institut.si

Hungary - hatter@hatter.hu

Lithuania - office@gay.lt

Greece - enact-project@kmop.org

**For further reading, you may find
the national reports, [here](#).**